

THE INNOVATIVE METHOD OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION

Traditional methods of teaching foreign languages such as rote memorization and grammar drills may not be effective for everyone, as they can be monotonous and unengaging. Many innovative methods of teaching foreign languages have emerged, which make the learning process more fun, interactive, and engaging. In this article, we will discuss some of the innovative methods of teaching foreign languages that have gained popularity in recent years.

Keywords. Method, communicative language teaching, modern foreign language, Cooperative Language Learning, Content-Based Teaching, Task-Based Teaching, Gamification, Conversation practice, Multimedia resources, innovative methods, 'teacher-fronted'

In today's globalized world, the ability to communicate in foreign languages has become increasingly important. However, traditional methods of teaching foreign languages, such as rote memorization and grammar drills, can be tedious and ineffective for many learners. In response to this, educators around the world have been exploring innovative and engaging methods of teaching foreign languages.

Learning a foreign language has become increasingly important in today's globalized world, where people from different cultures and backgrounds interact with each other on a daily basis. Traditional methods of teaching foreign languages such as rote memorization and grammar drills may not be effective for everyone,

as they can be monotonous and unengaging. As a result, many innovative methods of teaching foreign languages have emerged, which make the learning process more fun, interactive, and engaging. In this article, we will discuss some of the innovative methods of teaching foreign languages that have gained popularity in recent years.

Language instruction has received a lot of attention during the past century as a general professional field in the education industry. However, the idea of "method" was the bottleneck, the center of this idea, and as a result, it attracted the most attention. This idea depicts education as a series of methodical, research-based instructional techniques. It may be described simply as a method of connecting theory and practice. Methods are the systems for teaching that are often set with the essential procedures and strategies. The era of techniques spans from the 1950s to the 1980s. Situational Language Teaching and Audio-Lingualism were the two primary schools that were addressed about language teaching approaches.

Since its inception in the early 1970s, at least in Western contexts, communicative language teaching (CLT), with its emphasis on "what it means to know a language and to be able to put that knowledge to use in communicating with people in a variety of settings and situations," has taken center stage in school modern foreign language (MFL) programs. (East, 2019). The term "innovation" is frequently used to refer to something that is "new" or "enhanced" in some way, but only when it is effectively put into practice. (De Lano et al., 1994) identified four important terms that describe innovation. 1- Modify 2 - Growth 3. Novelty; 4. Development.

The word "approach" is more appropriate than "methods" to describe Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), which was formerly one of the cutting-edge techniques employed. The Natural Approach, Cooperative Language Learning, Content-Based Teaching, and Task-Based Teaching were all emerging at the same time as CLT. (1991 Rogers). It was observed that mastering good

communication in a foreign tongue has evolved into a key objective of many language programs all over the world.

One of the most effective ways of learning a foreign language is immersion, which involves learning the language by being immersed in the culture and environment where it is spoken. This method of teaching foreign languages requires students to constantly use the language in real-life situations, which helps them to develop fluency and confidence. Immersion can take many forms, including language exchanges, study abroad programs, and language immersion schools.

Gamification is a teaching method that involves using game design elements and mechanics to make learning more enjoyable and engaging. This method of teaching foreign languages is based on the idea that learning can be fun and that games can help to reinforce language concepts and vocabulary. Gamification can take many forms, including language learning apps, quizzes, and interactive games.

Conversation practice is a method of teaching foreign languages that involves engaging students in real-life conversations with native speakers of the language. This method of teaching foreign languages helps students to improve their pronunciation, fluency, and comprehension skills. Conversation practice can take many forms, including language exchange programs, online language learning communities, and language immersion programs.

Multimedia resources are a teaching method that involves using a variety of multimedia resources such as videos, audio recordings, and interactive apps to teach foreign languages. This method of teaching foreign languages is based on the idea that different types of media can help to reinforce language concepts and improve comprehension. Multimedia resources can take many forms, including language learning apps, podcasts, and interactive language learning websites.

Task-based learning is a method of teaching foreign languages that involves engaging students in real-life tasks that require them to use the language in a meaningful way. This method of teaching foreign languages helps students to develop their communication skills and improve their ability to use the language in

real-life situations. Task-based learning can take many forms, including role-playing, group projects, and problem-solving tasks.

One such method is the communicative approach, which focuses on the use of language for communication rather than just the memorization of vocabulary and grammar rules. In this approach, learners are encouraged to engage in authentic conversations with their peers and teachers, which helps them develop their speaking and listening skills in a meaningful way. This approach also emphasizes the importance of context, as learners are taught to use language in specific situations and for specific purposes.

Another innovative method of teaching foreign languages is the use of technology. With the rise of digital tools and platforms, educators can incorporate a variety of interactive and multimedia resources into their language classes. For example, language learning apps and websites can provide learners with opportunities to practice their skills through games, quizzes, and interactive exercises. Virtual reality and augmented reality technologies can also be used to create immersive language learning experiences, where learners can practice their skills in realistic simulated environments.

Another effective method of teaching foreign languages is the task-based approach, which focuses on using language in real-life tasks and situations. In this approach, learners are presented with a specific task or project to complete, such as ordering food in a restaurant or planning a trip, and are then guided through the process of using language to accomplish that task. This approach helps learners develop their language skills in a practical and relevant way, while also fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

It was anticipated that a teacher's ability to instruct in a communicative and creative manner would be difficult given their lack of experience in the subject. The majority of instructors are not native speakers and lack the competency needed to interact with pupils effectively. In many situations, teachers were ignorant of cutting-edge techniques. Traditions have been observed to occasionally play a part

in this as well. The fact that the primary tests for admissions and also for acquiring some employment were more conventional focused was one of the major problems.

To strengthen motivation and ensure interactive participation in the learning process, teaching goals must be established in accordance with the needs, deficiencies, and necessities of the targeted student population and educational environment, whether we choose to use traditional or innovative methods. (2017) Nurutdinova et al. According to research, instructors interpret and apply the concept in a number of ways that frequently incorporate more conventional and 'teacher-fronted' features when they meet the day-to-day reality of working with actual kids in real classrooms.

Finally, the use of games and gamification can also be an effective method of teaching foreign languages. By incorporating game elements, such as points, badges, and leaderboards, into language learning activities, educators can make the learning process more engaging and motivating for learners. Language learning games can also provide learners with opportunities to practice their skills in a fun and low-pressure environment, while also receiving feedback and reinforcement.

In conclusion, there are many innovative methods of teaching foreign languages that educators can use to engage and motivate learners. Whether it's through the use of technology, task-based learning, or gamification, these methods can help learners develop their language skills in a meaningful and practical way. By embracing these innovative methods, educators can create more effective and engaging language learning experiences for their students.

